

ENVIRONMENTALLY INDUCED TWIST IN THIN WALLED
COMPOSITE TUBES

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Summary

Unsymmetrical thin walled composite tubes are shown to exhibit substantial axial twist when subject to environmental changes such as moisture dryout and temperature changes. Laminate theory and a NASTRAN finite element model were employed to correlate experimental results. Two pairs of displacement transducers showed that the axial twist for a 90/0/±45 tube of HMS/3501-6 graphite epoxy and length to diameter ratio of 6 is about 3×10^{-4} radians for each percent moisture content and 4×10^{-6} radian/°C, in good agreement with theory. Predictions for other layups are also presented.

Introduction

Composite cylinders find many applications where dimensional stability is critical to meeting system requirements. High stiffness, low expansion graphite-epoxy tubes are major candidates for large space structures where thermal cycling in vacuo is expected. Since light weight is critical, the relatively few plies employed frequently result in unsymmetrical and/or unbalanced laminate ply layups. This normally leads to bending-stretching coupling effects and both in-plane and bending anisotropy. Theoretically, one effect of either thermal loading or a change in the amount of absorbed moisture on cylindrical, laminated shells is axial twist, both around the centerline of the tube and about the midplane of the laminate. These effects will vary with lamina properties and ply layup. A possible consequence of twist caused by either thermal or moisture content changes is the imposition of unacceptable residual stresses into an adhesively or mechanically bonded end fitting or joint. This may cause distortion of the overall structure and through stress relief due to microcracking, lead to loss of stiffness and damping capabilities of a large truss structure.

Analytical

Prediction of the axial twist of thin-walled composite cylinders was based on a finite element model (NASTRAN) and an analytical approach using linear elastic laminate theory. These are described briefly and predictions for various ply layups are presented.

In the NASTRAN finite element model (MSC Version 62A, Nov. 1982) the tube was modeled with 15 rings of 24 elements each, with each element spanning 15° circumferentially. Nodal locations along the meridian were evenly spaced at every 2 inches (5.08 cm) for the 30 inch (76.2 cm) tube model. Radially, nodes were located so as to lie along the middle surface of the tube wall. A total of 360 QUAD 4 plate elements was used for the overall tube geometry. Analytical boundary constraints were provided at the lower end of the tube. All translational degrees of freedom (DOF) along with tangential and meridional directions were restrained at the base of the tube, but the base-end is free for radial motion.

The analytical model starts with the inverted form of the constitutive stiffness equation for an elastic laminate in a state of plane stress;

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon^0 \\ K \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A' & B' \\ H' & D' \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N^N \\ M^N \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ^0 and K are the effective midplane strains and curvatures resulting from the nonmechanical stress and moment resultants N^N and M^N . The inverted stiffness matrices are given by Jones (1);

$$\begin{aligned} A' &= A^* - B^* D^{*-1} H^* \\ B' &= B^* D^{*-1} \\ H' &= -D^{*-1} H^* \\ D' &= D^{*-1} \\ A^* &= A^{-1} \\ B^* &= -A^{-1} B \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$H^* = BA^{-1}$$

$$D^* = D - BA^{-1}B$$

$$\text{and } A, B, D = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [\bar{Q}]_k (1, z, z^2) dz \quad (3)$$

where h is the lamina thickness and $[\bar{Q}]$ the transformed stiffness matrix for each k 'th ply. The principle quantity of interest is the shear strain at the outside of the tube. This is defined as

$$\gamma_{xy} = \gamma_{xy}^0 + zK_{xy} \quad (4)$$

where z is the distance from the midplane (see Figure 1). The midplane shear strain and K_{xy} terms are derived from equation (1) as

$$\gamma_{xy}^0 = A'_{16} N'_x + A'_{26} N'_y + A'_{66} N'_{xy} + B'_{16} M'_x + B'_{26} M'_y + B'_{66} M'_{xy} \quad (5)$$

$$K_{xy} = H'_{16} N'_x + H'_{26} N'_y + H'_{66} N'_{xy} + D'_{16} M'_x + D'_{26} M'_y + D'_{66} M'_{xy} \quad (6)$$

The subscripts x , y and z refer to the axial, circumferential and radial directions in a cylinder. Since the laminate plane is constrained as a tube the moments $M_x = M_y = 0$. The A_{16} and A_{26} terms are zero for a balanced laminate but the B matrix is not zero for an unsymmetrical layup. A similar expression for γ_{xy}^0 in terms of A^* and B^* matrices was given by Whitney and Halpin (2). A xy point stress laminate code by Reed (3) can be used to calculate the stiffness matrices in equations 1-6.

Figure 1. Diagram of tube showing coordinate system used for analysis and locations of LVDTs (numbered 0 to 9). The arrows indicate positive direction of displacement.

The amount of shear deformation in a plate is equal to the rotation of a tube about its axis or,

$$\gamma_{xy} L = R\theta \quad (7)$$

where θ is the angle of rotation shown in Figure 1. We then define a twist per unit non-mechanical parameter for a tube of length L and radius R as

$$\frac{d\theta}{dT} = \frac{\Delta\gamma_{xy}^T}{\Delta T} \frac{L}{R} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d\theta}{dM} = \frac{\Delta\gamma_{xy}^M}{\Delta M} \frac{L}{R} \quad (9)$$

Here T and M represent units of temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and moisture (% by weight), since the lamina coefficients are normally given in these units. The twist may also be expressed as an angle θ per unit non-mechanical parameter per unit length of tube. For example,

$$\frac{d\theta}{dT} \left(\frac{1}{L}\right) = \frac{\Delta\gamma_{xy}^T}{\Delta T} \frac{1}{R} \quad (10)$$

Here we shall use equations (8) and (9), bearing in mind that $d\theta/dT$ and $d\theta/dM$ apply to a 30 inch (76.2 cm) tube with a 0.01968 inch (0.05) wall thickness.

Table I gives the input material parameters. Tables II and III give predicted values of the shear strain and $d\theta/dM$ and $d\theta/dT$, respectively, for a variety of ply layups as calculated by the NASTRAN model. It is seen that there is a wide range of predicted twist values, with the highest values being found for unsymmetrical layups such as 90/0/ \pm 45. (The sign of the $d\theta/dM$ or $d\theta/dT$ values depends on the environmental parameter change; in tables II and III we assumed a $+1^{\circ}\text{C}$ change and a $+1\%$ moisture change). Figure 2 illustrates the distortion in three dimensions predicted for the tube from the NASTRAN model for a $+1\%$ moisture change. The axial and radial deformations dominate; the twist is contained within the broadening of the vertical line elements.

TABLE I. Input Lamina Constituent Properties

Property	Unit	HMS/3501-6	GY70/934
E_1	msi (GPa)	30(207)	44(303)
E_2	msi (GPa)	1.05(7.24)	0.975(6.72)
ν_{12}	-	0.25	0.192
G_{12}	msi (GPa)	0.65(4.48)	0.71(4.90)
Ply Thickness	in(mm)	.005(0.127)	.005(0.127)
α_1	$10^{-6}^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$	-0.63	-1.04
α_2	$10^{-6}^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$	28.8	25.95
β_1	$10^{-6}\%M^{-1}$	60	59
β_2	$10^{-6}\%M^{-1}$	5900	3199

TABLE II
Moisture NASTRAN Predicted
Twist of Laminate Tube (30 inches)

HMS/3501-6	$d\theta/dM$ (Rad./%M)	γ_{xy}^M (In./In./%M)
90/±45/0	1.305×10^{-4}	1.087×10^{-5}
0/±45/90	-2.183×10^{-4}	-1.819×10^{-5}
90/0/±45	2.231×10^{-4}	1.859×10^{-5}
0/90/±45	-6.125×10^{-6}	-5.104×10^{-7}
(0/90) _S	-5.497×10^{-13}	-4.581×10^{-14}
<u>GY70/934</u>		
(±30) _S	7.113×10^{-12}	5.927×10^{-13}
(±45) _S	-5.587×10^{-12}	-4.656×10^{-13}
0/±60/0	-2.192×10^{-5}	-1.827×10^{-6}
(0/45/90/135) _{2S}	-5.206×10^{-13}	-4.338×10^{-14}

TABLE III
Temperature NASTRAN Predicted
Twist of Laminate Tube (30 inches)

HMS/3501-6	$d\theta/dT$ (Rad./°C)	γ_{xy}^T (In./In./°C)
90/±45/0	6.592×10^{-7}	5.493×10^{-8}
0/±45/90	-1.103×10^{-6}	-0.919×10^{-7}
90/0/±45	1.126×10^{-6}	-0.938×10^{-7}
0/90/±45	-3.103×10^{-8}	-2.586×10^{-9}
(0/90) _S	-1.373×10^{-15}	-1.144×10^{-16}
<u>GY70/934</u>		
(±30) _S	1.155×10^{-13}	0.962×10^{-14}
(±45) _S	1.393×10^{-14}	1.161×10^{-15}
0/±60/0	-1.884×10^{-7}	1.57×10^{-8}
(0/45/90/135) _{2S}	1.448×10^{-15}	1.206×10^{-16}

Figure 2. NASTRAN model assuming a 30 inch (76.2 cm) tube with a 2.5 inch (6.35 cm) radius after moisture content change (1% M).

Experimental

Due to its high predicted value of $d\theta/dT$ or $d\theta/dM$, a 4-ply unsymmetrical tube of HMS/3501-6 with a 90/0/±45 layup was chosen for study. The tube was 86 cm long with a 12.7 cm inner diameter and had been subjected to numerous thermal cycling tests in vacuo before storage at 22°C at 50% relative humidity for several years. In this experiment the tube was surrounded by a quartz rod frame on which ten precision Trans-Tek (4) linear variable differential transformers (LVDT's) were attached with VARIAN TORR-SEAL low outgassing epoxy. This vacuum adhesive was used to attach the ultra low expansion glass rods to the metal core rod and the other end of the glass to the tube. The epoxy binder for the coil assembly was enclosed in a steel housing, helping to minimize dryout effects in vacuo. The scale factor was 30 ± 1 volts/inch displacement for a range of ± 0.050 in. with a $\pm 0.5\%$ full scale linearity. The LVDT's were calibrated for the temperature range $\pm 60^\circ\text{C}$ and the resolution was theoretically infinite. In our case a data logger recorded the outputs to 0.0001 volts, equivalent to a displacement of 0.087 microns.

Figure 3 shows the frame with a similar test sample. The mode of mounting (LVDT's #7 and 8 in the lower foreground) is shown. The aluminum foil covered heater is positioned between the test sample and quartz rod frame when the entire assembly is located in the vacuum chamber, shown at right. The heater consists of glass tubes with Nichrome coiled wire resistance heaters. The tube is supported on a quartz tube stand. The twist was measured by LVDT's # 3 and #4 in one plane separated by 30 inches from #7 and #8 in the lower plane. The entire vacuum chamber rested on compressed air for vibration stability. The vacuum pressure was reduced to 150 mTorr after 1/2 hour and stayed at 15 mTorr after 3 hours.

Figure 3. Test apparatus showing quartz frame, LVDT's, heater, data logger and vacuum chamber.

Data Analysis

Since the output of the LVDTs depends on the total quantity of the metal core within the coil cavity, one may expect little effect from purely transverse displacements of the glass probe tip. Consequently, the analysis assumes that the LVDT outputs reflect only the y directions (hoop) displacement (for LVDT's #3, 4, 7 and 8), and that these outputs are unaffected by changes in the tube length or diameter. If θ is the angle of rotation about the tube axis, the displacements of these LVDTs will be

$$\Delta(\text{LVDT}) = R \sin\theta + \Delta C \quad (9)$$

where

$$\Delta C = [\Delta(\text{LVDT})_a + \Delta(\text{LVDT})_b] / 2 \quad (10)$$

ΔC represents any shift in the axis of the tube in the direction of the coplanar LVDT's a or b (e.g. 3 and 4 or 7 and 8). By combining these equations the angular twists can be expressed as

$$\Delta\theta \text{ (radians)} = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta 4 - \Delta 3}{2R\phi} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta 8 - \Delta 7}{2R\phi} \right) \quad (11)$$

where ϕ is the LVDT characteristic (30V/in).

Results

Moisture Dryout

Figure 4 shows the displacements of the four points on the tube surface needed to calculate the twist (#3,4,7 and 8). The LVDT numbered 0,

which is also shown in the figure, and #1 measuring the axial motion gave identical results within a few tenths of microns. The dashed lines indicate that no data were taken during these periods.

Figure 4. Motion of five LVDT's during tube dryout. (30 V = 1 inch displacement).

Figure 5 compares the present results to earlier data (5) taken on the same tube by a laser interferometer. The axial $\Delta L/L$ data are plotted against $1 - \exp(-\sqrt{t}/\tau)$ where τ is proportional to the square of the tube thickness divided by the diffusivity. Its value is 17.48, based on a least squares fit to laser data for this tube. Figure 7 shows that after about 40 hours the slopes of the LVDT data are identical to the earlier laser data. The LVDT data extrapolate to a value of $\Delta L/L$ at $t = \infty$ of about $109 \mu\text{in/in}$ while the laser data gave a value of $122 \mu\text{in/in}$. Partial dryout during setup could explain some of the offset to longer times for the LVDT case. A change in coefficient of moisture expansion (CME) should also give a different final $\Delta L/L$ value.

Application of equation (11) to the data of Figure 4 yields the twist data in Figure 5. Extrapolation to $t = \infty$ suggests the final twist on complete dryout would be $\Delta\theta$ of about 2.2×10^{-4} radians. Allowing for slight dryout prior to vacuum application, total ΔM is about 0.7%, so that $d\theta/dM$ measured is $22 \times 10^{-5} \div 0.7$ or 3.1×10^{-4} rad/%M.

Figure 5. Dryout data for GY70/934 tube sample. Lines represent axial shrinkage while data points refer to present twist data obtained with LVDT's.

Heating

Figure 6 presents LVDT data during heating to 60°C in vacuo after 430 hours in vacuo at 24°C. The measured total twist was 1.57×10^{-4} radians for the 36°C excursion. The axial expansion gave an effective CTE (α_x) of $3.53 \times 10^{-7} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. It is slightly high as expansion of the quartz stand adds to the effective (negative) displacement of LVDT #0 or #1. Prior measurements with a laser interferometer gave a CTE of $\sim 2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ in this temperature range so that the agreement is considered satisfactory.

Table IV summarizes the results and compares them to the predicted values.

TABLE IV
Results of Twist Measurements and Predictions
HMS/3501-6, 90/0/±45 Tube

A) <u>MOISTURE</u>	<u>dθ/dM</u>
Measured for 30" tube	$3.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ rad}/\%M$
NASTRAN model	$2.23 \times 10^{-4} \text{ rad}/\%M$
B) <u>TEMPERATURE</u>	<u>dθ/dT</u>
Measured for 30" tube	$4.36 \times 10^{-6} \text{ rad}/^\circ\text{C}$
NASTRAN model	$1.13 \times 10^{-6} \text{ rad}/^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 6. Displacements of five LVDT's during heating of dried tube sample. Heating rate was about 2°C/min.

Discussion

Repeated excursions to below -30°C causes considerable microcracking in HMS/3501-6 tubes with 90, ± 45 and 0° plies (See Wolff (6)). This tube had been cooled to -100°C at least six times before the LVDT data were taken. Thermally induced microcracking will affect the CTE through reduction in E_{22} and/or G_{12} . It can be shown by laminate theory that a reduction in E_{22} from 1.05×10^6 psi to 0.84×10^6 psi will reduce the axial CTE from $5.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ to about the measured value of $3.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$. At the same time this will reduce the CME by about 15%, so that for the same initial moisture content the $\Delta L/L$ at $t = \infty$ and 24°C will be reduced from 122 to 104 $\mu\text{in/in}$. The extrapolated value of 109 $\mu\text{in/in}$ in Figure 5 is a good approximation. A reduction in E_{22} will also reduce the predicted value of $d\theta/dT$ and $d\theta/dM$. Another uncertainty in twist prediction is accurate knowledge of β_{22} , the transverse ply CME.

The results agree well with those predicted by the NASTRAN model. The laminate theory gave consistent relative values for the various layups, but the values tended to be high. The manner of constraint of the plate curvatures by the tube configuration is suggested as a possible explanation for the discrepancy, and further investigation is recommended.

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